

PYRONES AND RELATED COMPOUNDS. PART I FORMATION AND STRUCTURE OF 2:6-DIHYDROXY-1:4-PYRONE.

By R. KAUSHAL.

2:6-Dihydroxy-1:4-pyrone has been obtained from acetone dicarboxylic acid and its various derivatives have been described.

Pechmann and Neger (*Annalen*, 1893, 273, 186) found that the action of acetic anhydride on acetone dicarboxylic acid is unusual as the reagent acetylates the acid at the carbon instead of at the hydroxylic oxygen yielding the acetylated product (I), which immediately changes to dehydro-acetocarboxylic acid (II).

According to them if purified acetone dicarboxylic acid is used in place of the crude one containing sulphuric acid, the yield of (II) is much decreased.

By shaking pure acetone dicarboxylic acid (free from sulphuric acid) with acetic anhydride Willstätter and Pfannenstien (*Annalen*, 1921, 422, 7) obtained the anhydride (III) of acetone dicarboxylic acid having the same melting point as the acid namely 137°.

Willstätter's experiment was repeated and it was found that at comparatively low temperature (about 20°), the anhydride (III) is formed but at room temperature (about 30°) a new substance is produced which melted at 94° and which is found to be an isomer of (III). The isomer differs from the anhydride in the following respects :—

(i) The anhydride readily dissolves in water to form the acid while the isomer is stable and could be crystallised from hot water.

(ii) It dissolves in cold alkalis from which it is recovered unchanged on quickly acidifying. But with hot aqueous alkali it is decomposed.

(iii) It can be crystallised from hot alcohol with which the anhydride forms the acid-ester of acetone dicarboxylic acid.

(iv) It forms a nitrophenylhydrazone melting at 215°, while the anhydride does not. Acetone dicarboxylic acid, however, forms a nitrophenylhydrazone melting at 153°.

The anhydride changes into the isomer in contact with hot acetic anhydride, while in contact with aqueous hydrochloric acid or sulphuric acid the isomer changes gradually into the acetone dicarboxylic acid, the presence of which is confirmed by the formation of addition product with boiling mercuric sulphate solution (Deniges, *Compt. rend.*, 1898, 128, 680). The change of the isomer into the acid is not instantaneous and obviously takes place *via* the anhydride.

The isomer, therefore, is 2:6-dihydroxy-1:4-pyrone (IV, R=OH). Like pyrones it forms a crystalline addition product with mercuric chloride but does not form a chloroplatinate or a picrate, probably because in the formation of these, hydrochloric acid is necessary in contact with which it changes into acetone dicarboxylic acid. It reacts with *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine which justifies the ketonic structure.

With methyl alcoholic ammonia at 0°, it forms the di-ammonium compound of 2:6-hydroxy-4-pyridone (V), which is being investigated further and will form part of a later communication.

With two molecules of phosphorus pentachloride the hydrochloride of 2:6-dichloropyrone results melting at 105°, from which by neutralising the hydrochloric acid the dichloropyrone (IV, R=Cl) is obtained.

With sodium ethylate in alcoholic solution a disodium compound (IV, R=ONa) is formed.

From the disodium compound and ethyl iodide in alcohol, 2,6-diethoxy-pyrone (IV, R=OEt) is produced. It is a pleasant smelling liquid, b.p. 65-68°/6 mm., which forms a crystalline addition product with mercuric chloride.

Acetyl chloride and acetic anhydride in the presence of a trace of sulphuric acid do not acetylate the dihydroxypyrrone but produce dehydroacetocarboxylic acid (II). Nevertheless, from the disodium compound of the pyrrone and 3:5-dinitrobenzoyl chloride in boiling benzene the dinitrobenzoate [IV, R = C₆H₃(NO₂)₂-CO-O], m.p. 90°, is produced.

Attempts to obtain a diphenylurethane resulted in the formation of diphenylurea, a tendency shown by most of the tertiary alcoholic compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Acetone dicarboxylic Anhydride (III).—To well-cooled acetic anhydride (8 g.) purified acetone dicarboxylic acid (4 g.) was added and the mixture was shaken, temperature being not allowed to rise above 20°. The acid went into solution and on keeping for $\frac{1}{4}$ hour in ice and shaking, the anhydride separated as prisms. It was filtered, washed with benzene and dried, m.p. 136-37° (decomp.) changing to a red liquid, yield 2 g.

2:6-Dihydroxy-4-pyrrone (IV, R=OH). Acetone dicarboxylic acid (50 g.), freed from sulphuric acid by crystallisation from acetic acid, was shaken at room temperature (30°) with acetic anhydride (100 g.) until the acid went into solution with slight evolution of heat. The solution was allowed to remain overnight, when the dihydroxypyrrone separated in shining plates and the colour had changed to red. It was filtered and washed with benzene. The filtrate on standing gave a second crop of the pyrrone, total yield of the crude product is 28 g. It crystallises from benzene in long shining needles, m.p. 94°. [Found: C, 47·2; H, 3·7. M.W., (by titration), 128·4. C₅H₄O₄ requires C, 46·8; H, 3·1 per cent. M.W., 128]. It develops a violet colour with ferric chloride.

The *nitrophenylhydrazine* separated as a yellow solid on mixing the dihydroxypyrrone and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine, separately dissolved in 50% acetic acid. It was filtered and washed with dilute acetic acid and crystallised from pyridine, m.p. 215°. (Found: N, 16·6. C₁₁H₉O₅N₃ requires N, 16·0 per cent).

The *mercuric chloride addition product* was obtained as a crystalline solid by mixing equivalent quantities of mercuric chloride and dihydroxypyrrone separately dissolved in ether and on evaporation of the solvent. It crystallised from water, m.p. 235° (decomp.). (Found: Hg, 50·8. C₅H₄O₄, HgCl₂ requires Hg, 50·2 per cent).

Conversion of Acetone dicarboxylic Anhydride into Dihydroxypyrrone.—The anhydride (0·5 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (1 g.) on

warming and left overnight. Next day on rubbing the pyrone separated in shining needles, yield 0.4 g. It was crystallised from benzene in shining needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with a genuine sample of the dihydroxypyrene 94°.

Conversion of Dihydroxypyrene into Acetone dicarboxylic Acid.—The dihydroxypyrene was left in contact with a trace of hydrochloric acid when it went into solution. The resulting solution on pouring into boiling aqueous mercuric sulphate gave a white crystalline product, which proved to be identical with the addition product $2 \text{ Hg C}_5\text{H}_4\text{O}_5$, HgSO_4 , 2 HgO . The addition product is insoluble in water and soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid. The presence of sulphuric acid, however, does not interfere in its formation.

Di-ammonium salt of 2 : 6-Dihydroxy-4-pyridone.—The dihydroxypyrene (2 g.) was added to well-cooled saturated methyl alcoholic ammonia (15 c.c.), and the solution was kept in ice for 2 hours when the ammonium compound separated as clusters of needles. It was filtered, washed with methyl alcohol and dried on a porous plate, m.p. 97° with sintering at 92°, yield almost quantitative. It is very hygroscopic and it gives a violet colour with aqueous ferric chloride. It is very soluble in water and dilute hydrochloric acid. With cold caustic soda it evolves ammonia. (Found : N, 22.2. $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{N}$, 2NH_3 , CH_3OH requires N, 21.76 per cent) A similar compound, *viz.*, ammonium salt of 2 : 6-dihydroxy-4-pyridone semicarbazone has been recently described by Jacini (*Gazzetta*, 1937, 67, 715).

Hydrochloride of Dichloropyrene was prepared from dihydroxypyrene (4.5 g., 1 mol.) and phosphorus pentachloride (15 g., 2 mol.). After keeping in boiling water for 5 minutes the reaction mixture was added to water when a paste was obtained which on extraction with boiling water and cooling deposited the dichloropyrene hydrochloride in thin silky plates, m.p. 103.4°, yield 1.2 g. If, however, the liquid after the reaction was distilled under reduced pressure after removing phosphorus oxychloride, it distilled at 110–130°/4 mm. with much decomposition, and it gradually solidified to colourless needles. Probably the hydrochloride during distillation dissociates into the dichloropyrene and hydrochloric acid.

The hydrochloride crystallises from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 105°. [Found : C, 30.6 ; H, 1.7 ; Cl, 53.4 ; M.W. (by titration), 196. $\text{C}_5\text{H}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2$, HCl requires C, 29.8, H, 1.5 ; Cl, 52.8 per cent. M.W., 201.5 for monobasic].

2 : 6-Dichloro-4-pyrene (IV, R=Cl) was obtained from the hydrochloride by neutralising an alcoholic solution with 2*N*-caustic soda. The solution

was evaporated nearly to dryness at room temperature and the dichloropyrone was extracted with ethyl acetate. It crystallises as thick needles, m.p. 78-80°. (Found : Cl, 43·2. $C_5H_2O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 43·0 per cent).

Disodium compound of dihydroxypyrene was obtained by adding sodium ethylate prepared from 0·5 g. (2 atoms) of sodium with dihydroxypyrene (1·3 g., 1 mol.) in absolute alcohol. The sodium salt separating was filtered, washed with alcohol and finally with ether, yield 1·8 g. (Found in the compound dried at 120° for 6 hours : Na, 27·4. $C_5H_2O_4Na_2$ requires Na, 26·7 per cent).

2:6-Diethoxypyrene (IV, R = OC_2H_5).—To the suspension of the sodium derivative of dihydroxypyrene, prepared from 0·92 g. (2 atoms) of sodium to 2·5 g. (1 mol.) of dihydroxypyrene, dissolved in alcohol, ethyl iodide (7 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 8 hours with the addition of more ethyl iodide (2 g.). On distilling off the alcohol and acidification, the oil was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract was washed with dilute alkali and water, dried over calcium chloride and ether distilled. It distilled at 65-70°/6 mm., yield 1·5 g. (Found : C, 59·0 ; H, 6·6. $C_9H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 58·7 ; H, 6·6 per cent). The diethoxy compound is a colourless liquid with a pleasant camphor-like odour. It does not form a chloroplatinate or a picrate and it is insoluble in hydrochloric acid. In ethereal solution it forms an addition product with mercuric chloride, which was crystallised from water by evaporation of the solvent, m.p. 265° (decomp.).

Action of Acetyl Chloride and Acetic Anhydride on Dihydroxypyrene.—The dihydroxypyrene was heated with the reagents in presence of a few drops of sulphuric acid and the reaction mixture on pouring into water gave shining plates, m.p. 154°. It was identified to be dehydroacetocarboxylic acid by mixed m.p. and the formation of the potassium derivative.

Di-3 : 5-dinitrobenzoate of the dihydroxypyrene was obtained by refluxing on a water-bath for 8 hours the suspension of the sodium compound of the pyrene (1 mol.) in dry benzene and 3 : 5-dinitrobenzoyl chloride (2 mols). It was filtered and the filtrate deposited crystals. They were collected and washed with ether and then with alcohol. It crystallised from benzene-alcohol as needles, m.p. 90°. From 2 g. of the sodium compound 0·5 g. of the pure substance was obtained. (Found : C, 43·7 ; H, 1·4 ; N, 11·3. $C_{10}H_8O_{14}N_4$ requires C, 44·1 ; H, 1·55 ; N, 10·85 per cent).

Action of Phenylisocyanate on Dihydroxypyrene.—Equivalent quantities of the dihydroxypyrene and phenylisocyanate were mixed and the mixture gently heated for 10 minutes. On cooling a solid was obtained which was

filtered, washed with dilute caustic soda and finally crystallised from 90% alcohol as almost colourless prisms, m.p. 236-37°. (Found : N, 13.0 per cent). This proved to be diphenylurea, m.p. 238°.

The author wishes to express his gratefulness to Prof. S. S. Deshapande for his kind interest in the work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
HOLKAR COLLEGE, INDORE.

Received October 9, 1939
